

Predicting Power Utilization In Large Vehicles Using ML

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Abstract:

Instead of the conventional time period, we employed the vehicle trip distance while creating customized machine learning models for fuel use. Seven predictors generated from vehicle speed and road grade are combined with this method to create a highly predictive neural network model for average fuel consumption in large vehicles. To reduce fuel usage across the board, the suggested methodology can be quickly established and implemented for each individual vehicle in a fleet. The model's predictors are combined over predetermined window sizes for distance travelled. The evaluation of various window widths reveals that a 1 km window has a 0.91 coefficient of determination and a mean absolute peak-to-peak percent error that is less.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fuel consumption models for vehicles are of interest to manufacturers, regulators, and consumers. They are needed across all the phases of the vehicle life-cycle. In this paper, we focus on modeling average fuel consumption for heavy vehicles during the operation and maintenance phase. In general, techniques used to develop models for fuel consumption fall under three main categories: • Physics- based models, which are derived from an in depth understanding of the physical system. These models describe the

dynamics of the components of the vehicle at each time step using detailed mathematical equations [1], [2]. • Machine learning models, which are data-driven and represent an abstract mapping from an input space consisting of a selected set of predictors to an output space that represents the target output, in this case average fuel consumption [3], [4]. • Statistical models, which are also data-driven and establish a mapping between the probability distribution of a selected set of predictors and the target outcome [5], consumption fall under three main categories: • Physics- based models, which are derived from an in depth understanding of the

physical system. These models describe the dynamics of the components of the vehicle at each time step using detailed mathematical equations [1], [2].

- Machine learning models, which are data-driven and represent an abstract mapping from an input space consisting of a selected set of predictors to an output space that represents the target output, in this case average fuel consumption [3], [4].
- Statistical models, which are also data-driven and establish a mapping between the probability distribution of a selected set of predictors and the target outcome

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

It is suggested to create a model that may be simply constructed for each heavy vehicle in a sizable fleet. A fleet manager can optimise route planning for all of the vehicles in the fleet based on each individual vehicle's expected fuel consumption, ensuring that the route assignments are in line to reduce overall fleet fuel consumption.

Seven predictors generated from vehicle speed and road grade are combined with this method to create a highly predictive neural network model for average fuel consumption in large vehicles. A 1 km window has a 0.91 coefficient of determination and a mean absolute peak-to-peak percent inaccuracy when various window sizes are compared to forecast fuel usage.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are often used to develop digital models for complex systems.

The models proposed in [15] highlight some of the difficulties faced by machine learning models when the input and output have different domains.

In this study, the input is aggregated in the time domain over 10 minutes intervals and the output is fuel consumption over the distance traveled during the same time period.

The complex system is represented by a transfer function $F(p) = o$, where $F(\cdot)$ represents the system,

p refers to the input predictors and o is the response of the system or the output.

The ANNs used in this paper are Feed Forward Neural Networks (FNN).

Training is an iterative process and can be performed using multiple approaches including particle swarm optimization [20] and back propagation. Other approaches will be considered in future work in order to evaluate their ability to improve the model's predictive accuracy.

ADVANTAGES

Data is collected at a rate that is proportional to its impact on the outcome. When the input space is sampled with respect to time, the amount of data collected from a vehicle at a stop is the same as the amount of data collected when the vehicle is moving.

The predictors in the model are able to capture the impact of both the duty cycle and the environment on the average fuel consumption of the vehicle (e.g., the number of stops in an urban traffic over a given distance).

Data from raw sensors can be aggregated on-board into few predictors with lower storage and transmission bandwidth requirements. Given the increase in computational capabilities of new vehicles, data summarization is best performed on-board near the source of the data.

IV. RESULT

V. CONCLUSION

This paper Machine learning model that can be conveniently developed for each heavy vehicle in a fleet.

The model relies on seven predictors: number of stops, stop time, average moving speed, characteristic acceleration, aerodynamic speed squared, change in kinetic energy and change in potential energy.

The last two predictors are introduced in this paper to help capture the average dynamic behavior of the vehicle. All of the predictors of the model are derived from vehicle speed and road grade.

These variables are readily available from telematics devices that are becoming an integral part of connected vehicles. Moreover, the predictors can be easily computed on-board from these two variables.

In this paper author is describing concept to predict average fuel consumption in heavy vehicles using Machine Learning Algorithm such as ANN (Artificial Neural Networks). To predict fuel consumption author has extracted 7 predictor features from heavy vehicle dataset

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